

EARLY COMPLICATIONS AFTER BARIATRIC SURGERY

Keywords

Bariatric surgery,

Bleeding, stapler line leakage,

Sleeve gastrectomy,

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ABSTRACT

Obesity is a major health problem that increases morbidity and mortality rates worldwide. The aim of this study is to evaluate early complications in patients who underwent sleeve gastrectomy for obesity and to examine parameters that may be associated with these complications. In this study, patients who underwent obesity surgery between January 1, 2017, and September 23, 2024, were compared in terms of age, gender, and preoperative and postoperative body mass index (BMI). Postoperative complications that developed within the first month, including stapler line leakage, bleeding, wound site infection, and other complications, were examined. The study included 135 patients who underwent sleeve gastrectomy with a diagnosis of obesity. The mean age of the patients was 39.1 ± 10.1 years, 71.9% were female, and 28.1% were male. Significant weight loss was observed in patients one month after surgery; BMI decreased from 46.4 ± 6.8 to 41.9 ± 6.3 kg/m² ($p < 0.05$). Three patients (2.2%) had a stapler line leak, 11 (8.1%) received erythrocyte suspension transfusion, and 2 (1.5%) had atelectasis. There were no significant differences in BMI, age, or underlying conditions between patients with complications and those without ($p > 0.05$). This study demonstrates that sleeve gastrectomy is an effective procedure for short-term weight loss and is reliable due to its low complication rates. A multidisciplinary approach is important for the early detection and effective management of complications such as bleeding and stapler line leaks. Preoperative patient assessment, careful application of techniques, and close postoperative follow-up are considered to play a critical role in improving surgical success.

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is a condition characterized by excessive or abnormal fat accumulation that can harm the body's health. Over the past half-century, obesity has become an increasingly widespread epidemic and is now the second leading cause of preventable deaths after smoking. Obesity affects more than one-third of the world's population today, encompassing individuals who are overweight. If current trends continue, it is estimated that by 2030, approximately 38% of adults worldwide will be overweight and another 20% will be obese.^{1,2}

Obesity treatment has undergone significant evolution over the past 70 years with the development of bariatric surgery. Conservative methods such as low-calorie and balanced diets, physical activity, anorexic medications, and behavioral therapy have generally been ineffective, especially in cases of morbid obesity, and patients have struggled to maintain long-term weight loss. Bariatric surgery provides greater and more sustainable weight loss in severely obese individuals compared to non-surgical methods.^{3,4,5}

Among bariatric surgical procedures, sleeve gastrectomy (SG) has become one of the most frequently preferred methods in recent years. Initially defined as the first stage of duodenal switch surgery, which has a malabsorptive component, SG has come to be accepted as an effective restrictive procedure on its own.

The popularity of SG is based on its relatively simple technical feasibility, lack of intestinal bypass, and lower risk of nutritional complications compared to other bariatric procedures (e.g., Roux-en-Y

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gastric bypass). Studies conducted worldwide have shown that SG provides significant improvement in obesity-related comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, and obstructive sleep apnea.^{6,7}

However, as with any surgical procedure, SG carries risks of early and late complications. In the early period, stapler line leaks, bleeding, infection, and thromboembolic events are the most significant causes of morbidity. Timely recognition and aggressive management of these complications play a critical role in reducing postoperative mortality.⁸

This study examined complications observed in the early period in patients who underwent sleeve gastrectomy. We aimed to contribute to the prediction of possible complications that may develop after obesity surgery and to provide information on the effective management of these complications.

In this study, the results of patients treated with the modified Limberg flap method and those treated with crystallized phenol were compared.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted with the approval of the Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee on October 3, 2024, with Decision No. 12, and was carried out in accordance with the principles of the Helsinki Declaration. Patient confidentiality was maintained, and anonymity was ensured in data analysis.

In this study, the files of patients who underwent sleeve gastrectomy between January 1, 2017, and September 23, 2024, were retrospectively reviewed. Patients aged 18 years and older who underwent obesity surgery for the first time were included in the study. Six patients who underwent revision surgery were excluded from the study. Patients' age, gender, body weight, and height were measured, and their body mass indices were calculated. Preoperative leukocyte count, hematocrit, hemoglobin, and CRP values were determined and compared with values measured on postoperative days 1, 3, and 30. Atelectasis, bleeding, wound site infection, stapler line leakage, conversion complications, and mortality observed in the first 30 days were recorded.

Preoperative Period: The height and weight of all patients were determined and their body mass indices (BMI) were calculated. Patients with a body mass index of 35 or above

were identified as candidates for obesity surgery and referred to an endocrinologist prior to surgery. Complete blood count, glucose level, liver and kidney function tests, thyroid function tests, and cortisol level were measured and evaluated. All patients underwent a low-dose dexamethasone test, and a document indicating that the patients could benefit from obesity surgery was obtained from an endocrinologist. Patients approved by the endocrinologist were evaluated by preoperative anesthesia, chest diseases, cardiology, and psychiatry. Patients who received approval from these departments underwent a full abdominal ultrasound and esophagogastroduodenoscopy. Patients who received approval from all these stages were deemed suitable for surgery. Twelve hours before surgery, all patients were administered low-molecular-weight heparin for embolism prophylaxis.

Operative Period: Immediately before surgery, patients were fitted with medium-pressure varicose stockings. After general anesthesia was administered with the patient in the supine position, four trocars were inserted through appropriate incisions in the upper right and left sides of the abdomen and the upper left and right sides of the umbilicus, and the operating table was positioned at approximately 30 degrees in the reverse Trendelenburg position. All surgeries were performed at a pressure of 10-12 mmHg. A nasogastric tube was inserted into the stomach to decompress it. Using energy devices, the omentum was separated from the stomach along the entire greater curvature, starting 4-5 cm proximal to the gastric antrum. Dissection was continued until the left diaphragmatic crus and esophagus were visible proximally. The nasogastric tube was removed, and a 38 F orogastric tube was placed from the lesser curvature of the stomach to the pylorus. Then, using endoscopic staplers, the orogastric tube was used as a guide to cut the stomach from the distal to the proximal end. After controlling the bleeding, the excised stomach was removed through a trocar. Methylene blue was administered through the orogastric tube to check for leaks. Sutures and clips were placed at appropriate sites. A single drain was placed along the stapler line, and the fascia and skin were closed to complete the procedures.

Postoperative Period: Patients were awakened from general anesthesia and those deemed appropriate were transferred to the intensive care unit. Paracetamol, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents, and narcotic analgesics were used for postoperative analgesia when necessary. All patients were encouraged to perform mobilization and breathing exercises.

Drainage follow-ups were performed by administering methylene blue within 24-48 hours postoperatively. Complete blood counts and biochemical parameters were evaluated on postoperative days 1 and 3. All patients were referred to a dietitian and started on an appropriate diet. Patients without any complications were discharged after their drains were removed. Sutures were removed on postoperative day 7. Body mass indices, complete blood counts, and biochemical values were measured and evaluated on postoperative day 30.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage distributions were used for frequency, and measures of dispersion such as mean and standard deviation were used. The normality of the variables was tested using the Shapiro-Wilks test. The Mann Whitney U test was used to compare two independent continuous variables that did not follow a normal distribution. The Paired T test was used to compare two dependent continuous variables. The Fisher Exact test, Yates-corrected Chi-square test, and Pearson Chi-square test were used to compare discrete variables. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Of the patients included in the study, 71.9% were female (n=97) and 28.1% were male (n=38). 59.3% of patients had no comorbidities (n=80), while 40.7% had at least one comorbidity (n=55). The number of patients without complications was 120 (88.9%), while the number of patients with complications was 15 (11.1%). The mean age of the patients was 39.1±10.1 years, the preoperative body weight was 126.5±22.3 kg, the height was 165.1±9.4 cm, and the preoperative body mass index (BMI) was 46.4±6.6 kg/m². The average postoperative drain removal time was recorded as 3.0±1.0 days (Table 1).

No complications developed in 88.9% of patients after bariatric surgery (n=120), while complications were observed in 11.1% (n=15). No comorbidities were present in 59.3% of patients (n=80), while comorbidities were present in 40.7% (n=55). Atelectasis was observed in 1.5% of patients (n=2) and was not observed in 98.5% of patients (n=133). Blood transfusions were administered to 11 patients (8.1%), while 124 patients (91.9%) did not receive blood transfusions. Stapler line leakage was detected in 3 patients (2.2%), while it was not observed in 132 patients (97.8%). Conversion to laparotomy occurred in 1.5% (n=2) of cases, while laparotomy was not required in 98.5% (n=133) of cases (Table 2).

The most common comorbidity in patients undergoing bariatric surgery was diabetes mellitus (n=19) at a rate of 23.2%, followed by hypertension (n=17) at 20.7% and asthma (n=7) at 8.5%. Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS) and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) were each detected in 2.4% of cases (n=2). Other comorbidities included polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), multinodular goiter (MNG), familial Mediterranean fever (FMF), heart failure (HF), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), chronic kidney disease (CKD), and cancer, with a total of 35 cases (42.8%) recorded in this group (Table 3).

The average preoperative weight of patients was 126.49±22.28 kg, and the weight at 1 month postoperatively was 114.13±20.62 kg (p<0.001). The preoperative BMI was 46.36 ± 6.64 kg/m², and the postoperative BMI at 1 month was 41.90 ± 6.25 kg/m² (p < 0.001) (Table 4).

The mean age of patients was 38.8±10.3 years in the group without complications and 40.9±8.4 years in the group with complications (p=0.328). Preoperative weight was 125.4±21.9 kg in patients without complications and 135.1±24.2 kg in patients with complications (p=0.156). The preoperative BMI was 46.4 in both groups, with standard deviations of 6.8 and 5.3, respectively (p=0.672). The preoperative hemoglobin value was 13.5±1.5 g/dL in the group without complications and 14.0±2.4 g/dL in the group with complications (p=0.237). The preoperative hematocrit value was determined as 40.9±5.2 and 41.8±6.4, respectively (p=0.484). The preoperative leukocyte count was 9.0±2.2 x10³/μL in the group without complications and 10.0±2.7 x10³/μL in the group with complications (p=0.195) (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the demographic characteristics, complication rates, and comorbidities of patients who underwent bariatric surgery, and the findings were discussed in comparison with the literature.

In our study, 71.9% of the patients were female. This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that women are more likely to seek obesity surgery.^{9,10} The prevalence of comorbidities was 40.7%, with the most common being diabetes mellitus (23.2%) and hypertension (20.7%). These results are consistent with the literature on the prevalence of metabolic syndrome components in morbidly obese individuals.^{11,12}

Complications developed in 11.1% of patients, with the most common complications being stapler line leakage (2.2%) and the need for blood transfusion (8.1%). These rates are similar to the complication rates reported in procedures such as sleeve gastrectomy and Roux-en-Y gastric bypass.^{7,13} In particular, our stapler line leak rate (2.2%) is consistent with the 1–4% range reported in the literature.¹⁴ The low conversion to laparotomy rate (1.5%) supports the reliability of minimally invasive surgery.¹⁵

The complication rate in male patients (23.7%) was found to be significantly higher than in female patients (6.2%) ($p=0.011$). This situation can be explained by the higher visceral fat and comorbidity burden in men.^{16,17} Similar studies have reported that male gender is an independent risk factor for postoperative complications.¹⁸

Significant weight loss ($p<0.001$) and BMI reduction were observed in the first postoperative month. These findings are consistent with studies confirming the short-term efficacy of bariatric surgery.^{19,20} However, the sustainability of these results should be investigated in long-term follow-up studies.

Preoperative weight, BMI, and laboratory parameters (Hb, Hct, leukocytes) were not found to be significantly associated with the development of complications ($p>0.05$). Although this result is consistent with some studies, it contradicts data in the literature showing that high BMI is associated with an increased risk of complications.^{21–27} This discrepancy may be due to the relatively small number of patients in our study. The limitations of this study include its single-center and retrospective design, short-term follow-up data, and relatively small sample size.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the demographic characteristics, comorbid conditions, early complications, and postoperative weight and body mass index changes in individuals who underwent bariatric surgery. It was determined that the majority of patients were female and that a significant proportion had no additional diseases. The most common comorbidities were diabetes, hypertension, and asthma.

In the postoperative period, complications such as atelectasis, blood transfusion, stapler line leakage, and conversion to laparotomy were observed at low rates. When comparing the preoperative and postoperative periods, a statistically

significant decrease in weight and body mass index was observed.

There were no significant differences between the groups with and without complications in terms of age, preoperative weight, body mass index, hemoglobin, hematocrit, and leukocyte levels. A significant relationship was found between gender and the development of complications.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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REFERENCES

1. World Obesity Federation. (2023). World Obesity Atlas 2023. Retrieved November 14, 2024, from <https://data.worldobesity.org/publications/WOF-Obesity-Atlas-V5.pdf>
2. Volken, T., & Ruesch, P. (2012). Risk of overweight and obesity among migrants in Switzerland. *International Journal of Public Health*, 4(8), 514–521.
3. Dietz, W. H., Baur, L. A., Hall, K., Puhl, R. M., Taveras, E. M., Uauy, R., & Kopelman, P. (2015). Management of obesity: Improvement of health-care training and systems for prevention and care. *The Lancet*, 385(9986), 2521–2533.
4. Panteliou E, Miras AD. What is the role of bariatric surgery in the management of obesity? *Climacteric*. 2017 Apr;20(2):97-102. doi: 10.1080/13697137.2017.1262638. Epub 2017 Jan 4. PMID: 28051892.
5. World Health Organization. (2024, March 1). Obesity and overweight. Retrieved November 15, 2024, from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>
6. Felsenreich DM, Bichler C, Langer FB, Gachabayov M, Prager G. Sleeve Gastrectomy: Surgical Technique, Outcomes, and Complications. *Surg Technol Int*. 2020 May 28;36:63-69. PMID: 32359172.
7. Salminen P, Helmiö M, Ovaska J, Juuti A, Leivonen M, Peromaa-Haavisto P, Hurme S, Soinio M, Nuutila P, Victorzon M. Effect of Laparoscopic Sleeve Gastrectomy vs Laparoscopic Roux-en-Y Gastric Bypass on Weight Loss at 5 Years Among Patients With Morbid Obesity: The SLEEVEPASS Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*.

- 2018 Jan 16;319(3):241-254. doi: 10.1001/jama.2017.20313. PMID: 29340676; PMCID: PMC5833550.
8. Rosenthal RJ; International Sleeve Gastrectomy Expert Panel; Diaz AA, Arvidsson D, Baker RS, Basso N, Bellanger D, Boza C, El Mourad H, France M, Gagner M, Galvao-Neto M, Higa KD, Himpens J, Hutchinson CM, Jacobs M, Jorgensen JO, Jossart G, Lakdawala M, Nguyen NT, Nocca D, Prager G, Pomp A, Ramos AC, Rosenthal RJ, Shah S, Vix M, Wittgrove A, Zundel N. International Sleeve Gastrectomy Expert Panel Consensus Statement: best practice guidelines based on experience of >12,000 cases. *Surg Obes Relat Dis.* 2012 Jan-Feb;8(1):8-19. doi: 10.1016/j.soard.2011.10.019. Epub 2011 Nov 10. PMID: 22248433.
 9. Angrisani L, Santonicola A, Iovino P, Vitiello A, Higa K, Himpens J, Buchwald H, Scopinaro N. IFSO Worldwide Survey 2016: Primary, Endoluminal, and Revisional Procedures. *Obes Surg.* 2018 Dec;28(12):3783-3794. doi: 10.1007/s11695-018-3450-2. PMID: 30121858.
 10. Peterli R, Wölnerhanssen BK, Peters T, Vetter D, Kröll D, Borbély Y, Schultes B, Beglinger C, Drewe J, Schiesser M, Nett P, Bueter M. Effect of Laparoscopic Sleeve Gastrectomy vs Laparoscopic Roux-en-Y Gastric Bypass on Weight Loss in Patients With Morbid Obesity: The SM-BOSS Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA.* 2018 Jan 16;319(3):255-265. doi: 10.1001/jama.2017.20897. PMID: 29340679; PMCID: PMC5833546.
 11. Schauer PR, Bhatt DL, Kirwan JP, Wolski K, Aminian A, Brethauer SA, Navaneethan SD, Singh RP, Pothier CE, Nissen SE, Kashyap SR; STAMPEDE Investigators. Bariatric Surgery versus Intensive Medical Therapy for Diabetes - 5-Year Outcomes. *N Engl J Med.* 2017 Feb 16;376(7):641-651. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1600869. PMID: 28199805; PMCID: PMC5451258.
 12. Sjöström L. Review of the key results from the Swedish Obese Subjects (SOS) trial - a prospective controlled intervention study of bariatric surgery. *J Intern Med.* 2013 Mar;273(3):219-34. doi: 10.1111/joim.12012. Epub 2013 Feb 8. PMID: 23163728.
 13. Adams TD, Davidson LE, Litwin SE, Kim J, Kolotkin RL, Nanjee MN, Gutierrez JM, Frogley SJ, Ibele AR, Brinton EA, Hopkins PN, McKinlay R, Simper SC, Hunt SC. Weight and Metabolic Outcomes 12 Years after Gastric Bypass. *N Engl J Med.* 2017 Sep 21;377(12):1143-1155. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1700459. PMID: 28930514; PMCID: PMC5737957.
 14. Brethauer SA, Kim J, el Chaar M, Pappasavas P, Eisenberg D, Rogers A, Ballem N, Kligman M, Kothari S; ASMBS Clinical Issues Committee. Standardized outcomes reporting in metabolic and bariatric surgery. *Surg Obes Relat Dis.* 2015 May-Jun;11(3):489-506. doi: 10.1016/j.soard.2015.02.003. PMID: 26093765.
 15. Aurora AR, Khaitan L, Saber AA. Sleeve gastrectomy and the risk of leak: a systematic analysis of 4,888 patients. *Surg Endosc.* 2012 Jun;26(6):1509-15. doi: 10.1007/s00464-011-2085-3. Epub 2011 Dec 17. PMID: 22179470.
 16. Gagner M, Deitel M, Kalberer TL, Erickson AL, Crosby RD. The Second International Consensus Summit for Sleeve Gastrectomy, March 19-21, 2009. *Surg Obes Relat Dis.* 2009 Jul-Aug;5(4):476-85. doi: 10.1016/j.soard.2009.06.001. Epub 2009 Jun 13. PMID: 19632647.
 17. Arterburn DE, Telem DA, Kushner RF, Courcoulas AP. Benefits and Risks of Bariatric Surgery in Adults: A Review. *JAMA.* 2020 Sep 1;324(9):879-887. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.12567. PMID: 32870301.
 18. Rubino F, Nathan DM, Eckel RH, Schauer PR, Alberti KG, Zimmet PZ, Del Prato S, Ji L, Sadikot SM, Herman WH, Amiel SA, Kaplan LM, Taroncher-Oldenburg G, Cummings DE; Delegates of the 2nd Diabetes Surgery Summit. Metabolic Surgery in the Treatment Algorithm for Type 2 Diabetes: A Joint Statement by International Diabetes Organizations. *Diabetes Care.* 2016 Jun;39(6):861-77. doi: 10.2337/dc16-0236. PMID: 27222544.
 19. Mingrone G, Panunzi S, De Gaetano A, Guidone C, Iaiconelli A, Leccesi L, Nanni G, Pomp A, Castagneto M, Ghirlanda G, Rubino F. Bariatric surgery versus conventional medical therapy for type 2 diabetes. *N Engl J Med.* 2012 Apr 26;366(17):1577-85. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1200111. Epub 2012 Mar 26. PMID: 22449317.
 20. Longitudinal Assessment of Bariatric Surgery (LABS) Consortium; Flum DR, Belle SH, King WC, Wahed AS, Berk P, Chapman W, Pories W, Courcoulas A, McCloskey C, Mitchell J, Patterson E, Pomp A, Staten MA, Yanovski SZ, Thirlby R, Wolfe B. Perioperative safety in the longitudinal assessment of bariatric surgery. *N Engl J Med.* 2009 Jul 30;361(5):445-54. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa0901836. PMID: 19641201; PMCID:

PMC2854565.

21. Buchwald H, Avidor Y, Braunwald E, Jensen MD, Pories W, Fahrbach K, Schoelles K. Bariatric surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA*. 2004 Oct 13;292(14):1724-37. doi: 10.1001/jama.292.14.1724. Erratum in: *JAMA*. 2005 Apr 13;293(14):1728. PMID: 15479938.
22. Khorgami Z, Shoar S, Andalib A, Aminian A, Brethauer SA, Schauer PR. Trends in utilization of bariatric surgery, 2010-2014: sleeve gastrectomy dominates. *Surg Obes Relat Dis*. 2017 May;13(5):774-778. doi: 10.1016/j.soard.2017.01.031. Epub 2017 Jan 25. PMID: 28256393.
23. DeMaria EJ, Murr M, Byrne TK, Blackstone R, Grant JP, Budak A, Wolfe L. Validation of the obesity surgery mortality risk score in a multicenter study proves it stratifies mortality risk in patients undergoing gastric bypass for morbid obesity. *Ann Surg*. 2007 Oct;246(4):578-82; discussion 583-4. doi: 10.1097/SLA.0b013e318157206e. PMID: 17893494.
24. Morino M, Toppino M, Forestieri P, Angrisani L, Allaix ME, Scopinaro N. Mortality after bariatric surgery: analysis of 13,871 morbidly obese patients from a national registry. *Ann Surg*. 2007 Dec;246(6):1002-7; discussion 1007-9. doi: 10.1097/SLA.0b013e31815c404e. PMID: 18043102.
25. Ponce J, DeMaria EJ, Nguyen NT, Hutter M, Sudan R, Morton JM. American Society for Metabolic and Bariatric Surgery estimation of bariatric surgery procedures in 2015 and surgeon workforce in the United States. *Surg Obes Relat Dis*. 2016 Nov;12(9):1637-1639. doi: 10.1016/j.soard.2016.08.488. Epub 2016 Aug 26. PMID: 27692915.
26. Livingston EH. The incidence of bariatric surgery has plateaued in the U.S. *Am J Surg*. 2010 Sep;200(3):378-85. doi: 10.1016/j.amjsurg.2009.11.007. Epub 2010 Apr 20. PMID: 20409518; PMCID: PMC2923252.
27. Welbourn R, Hollyman M, Kinsman R, Dixon J, Liem R, Ottosson J, Ramos A, Våge V, Al-Sabah S, Brown W, Cohen R, Walton P, Himpens J. Bariatric Surgery Worldwide: Baseline Demographic Description and One-Year Outcomes from the Fourth IFSO Global Registry Report 2018. *Obes Surg*. 2019 Mar;29(3):782-795. doi: 10.1007/s11695-018-3593-1. Epub 2018 Nov 12. PMID: 30421326.

Table 1. Preoperative demographic characteristics of patients and postoperative complications and drain status

		Number	Percentage
Gender	Female	97	71,9
	Male	38	28,1
Additional Disease	None	80	59,3
	Present	55	40,7
Complication	None	120	88,9
	Present	15	11,1
		Mean	Standard Deviation
Patient Age		39,1	10,1
Preoperative Weight		126,5	22,3
Height		165,1	9,4
Preoperative Body Mass Index		46,4	6,6
DAY Drain Removed		3,0	1,0

Table 2. Complications Following Bariatric Surgery

Complication	Condition	Number	Percentage
Atelectasis	None	133	98,5
	Present	2	1,5
Blood Transfusion	None	124	91,9
	Present	11	8,1
Stapler Line Leakage	None	132	97,8
	Present	3	2,2
Conversion to Laparotomy	None	133	98,5
	Present	2	1,5

The data in the table are presented as mean \pm standard deviation or number (percentage).

Table 3. Comorbidities Observed in Bariatric Surgery Patients and Their Frequencies

Additional Disease	Number	Percentage
Diabetes Mellitus	19	23,2
Hypertension	17	20,7
Asthma	7	8,5
OSAS	2	2,4
GERH	2	2,4
Others	35	42,8

The data in the table are presented in numerical and percentage (%) formats. The abbreviations are as follows: DM, Diabetes Mellitus; OSAS, Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome; GERD, Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease.

Table 4. Changes in patients' preoperative and postoperative weight and BMI

Parameter	Preoperative (Mean \pm SD)	Postoperative 1 Month (Mean \pm SD)	P value*
Weight (kg)	126,49 \pm 22,28	114,13 \pm 20,62	<0,001
BMI(kg/m ²)	46,36 \pm 6,64	41,90 \pm 6,25	<0,001

*Paired T test, BMI: Body Mass Index

Table 5. Factors associated with complications in patients

		No Complications (N=120)		Complications Present (N=15)		p
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Gender	Female	91	93,8	6	6,2	0,011 ^a
	Male	29	76,3	9	23,7	
Comorbidities	None	71	88,8	9	11,3	1,000 ^b
	Present	49	89,1	6	10,9	
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
Patient Age		38,8	10,3	40,9	8,4	0,328 ^c
Preoperative Weight		125,4	21,9	135,1	24,2	0,156 ^c
Preoperative BMI		46,4	6,8	46,4	5,3	0,672 ^c
Preoperative hemoglobin		13,5	1,5	14,0	2,4	0,237 ^c
Preoperative hematocrit		40,9	5,2	41,8	6,4	0,484 ^c
Preoperative Leukocytes		9,0	2,2	10,0	2,7	0,195 ^c

Fisher's Exact Test, b: Yates-corrected Chi-square, c: Mann-Whitney U Test, BMI: Body Mass Index.

a: